

Phytochemical Characterization and Inhibitory Mechanism of African Star Apple (*Chrysophyllum Albidum*) Ethanolic Seed Extract on Human Salivary A-Amylase

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Abstract

Chrysophyllum albidum, is a seasonal African fruit with notable therapeutic potential. This study investigated the interaction between its ethanolic seed extract and human salivary α -amylase (HSAmy), a key enzyme linked to carbohydrate digestion and type 2 diabetes using multi-spectroscopic approaches under simulated physiological intestinal conditions in a 25 mM citrate phosphate buffer, pH 6.8. Phytochemical screening and HPLC analysis of the seed extract was carried out and its anti-diabetic activity was assessed by HSAmy inhibition assay. The phytochemical screening analysis revealed the presence of key phytochemicals such as flavonoids, phenols, steroids, saponins, and terpenoids and major bioactive compounds which are linked to the extract's inhibitory activity when compared with standard inhibitor (acarbose). The extract showed concentration dependent inhibition of HSAmy, demonstrating its ability to slow down the digestion and absorption of carbohydrates, thereby reducing hyperglycemia, crucial in type 2 diabetes condition. The fluorescence quenching indicated that *C. albidum* quenches the intrinsic fluorescence of HSAmy following a mixed quenching mechanism accompanied by hydrophobic ($\Delta S^\circ > 0$ and $\Delta H^\circ > 0$), endothermic, spontaneous and entropy-driven process that was mainly tryptophan gated as revealed by synchronous spectroscopy. *C. albidum* was a mixed type inhibition for the enzyme. These findings support the potential use of *C. albidum* seed extract as a natural therapeutic agent for managing postprandial hyperglycemia.

Keywords: *Chrysophyllum albidum*, Phytochemicals, Human salivary α -amylase, Fluorescence spectroscopy, Hyperglycemia.

INTRODUCTION

Chrysophyllum albidum, commonly known as African star apple, is a plant species belonging to the family *Sapotaceae* (Udinyiwe and Aghedo, 2024). Native to various vegetation zones in Uganda, Nigeria, Niger Republic, Cameroon, and Côte d'Ivoire (Udinyiwe and Aghedo, 2024). This seasonal fruit is a staple in many African cultures and in Nigeria, it is popularly called Agbalumo in Yoruba land. The fruit is typically available during the dry season (December to March) and ranges from small to medium tree size. Research has shown that *C. albidum* possesses therapeutic, antiseptic, antifungal, and bacteriostatic activities due to its phenolic content

(Odewade and Odewade, 2023). The antioxidant properties of African star apple have consistently improved health by protecting the body against harmful radicals, which are implicated in the origin of many ailments such as cancer, cardiovascular diseases, diabetes mellitus, neural disorders, and arthritis. The therapeutic properties of African star apple can be linked to its phytochemical constituents (Agidew, 2022).

Alpha-Amylase (1,4- α -D-glucan-glucanohydrolase, EC3.2.1.1) is the primary digestive enzyme acting on starch or glycogen by breaking the internal α -1,4 glycosidic linkages between sugar molecules in polysaccharides through a hydrolysis reaction. It is an endoglycosidase which yields reaction products that retain α configuration. It is not to be confused with the exoglycosidases such as α -glucoamylase (or α -glucosidase), which cleave glucose residues sequentially from the nonreducing end, or with β -amylase, which yields reaction products in the β configuration (Das *et al.*, 2019).

Human salivary α -amylase (HSAmy) is a multifunctional enzyme produced by the serous acinar cells of the parotid and submandibular glands in the oral cavity of humans (Falese *et al.*, 2021). It initiates carbohydrate digestion in the mouth; and is one of the most common components in saliva, accounting for 10–20 % of the total protein content (Falese *et al.*, 2021). It plays a vital role in starch hydrolysis. Starch is a high molecular weight polymer of glucose. It is made up of amylose, a straight-chain α -1,4 linked polymer of about 10^5 units and amylopectin, a branched chain polymer with α -1,4 linked glucose with branch points made up of α -1,6 linkages that contains about 10^6 units of glucose. HSAmy cleaves the α -1,4 linkage when it is not next to a branch point or terminal glucose residue, thus, its products are maltose (2 glucose residues), maltotriose (3 glucose residues) and α -limit dextrins (5-6 residues which contain a branch point) (Falese *et al.*, 2021).

The African star apple (*Chrysophyllum albidum*) is known for its rich phenolic content, which contributes to its medicinal property (Odewade and Odewade, 2023). Previous researches has revealed the hypolipidemic and anti-hyperglycemic effects which can function in managing blood sugar levels and potentially providing therapeutic benefits for conditions like diabetes (Ajayi *et al.*, 2020). However, the inhibitory and binding mechanism of the plant seed extract with diabetes linked enzyme HSAmy is yet to be unraveled. Hence this research sought to provide insights into the inhibitory mechanism of interaction of the plant seed extract on HSAmy in managing blood sugar levels, which is essential for the treatment of Diabetes mellitus.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Collection

The fruits of *Chrysophyllum albidum* was purchased from a local market at Akure, Ondo State. Authentication was done at the Federal University of Technology Akure Herbarium, Centre for Research and Development (CERAD). The fruits were rinsed properly and the seeds were removed from it. Each seed was broken to yield cotyledon and seed coat. The cotyledons were dried at room temperature for 10 -14 days, pulverized into powder form and stored in air-tight containers at room temperature (25 °C) for further use.

Ethanollic Extraction

The sample powder (125g) was soaked 80% ethanol by stirring intermittently, for 72 hours and then filtered through Whatman no 1-filter paper and Millipore micro-syntax membrane filter (0.45mm syringe filters) before use. The filtrate was concentrated using rotary evaporator to

produce crude ethanolic extract of *Chrysophyllum albidium*. The seed extract was stored at 4 °C until further use.

Phytochemical Screening

The crude ethanolic seed extracts of *Chrysophyllum albidium* were tested for the presence of the following phytochemicals: Total Phenol, Total Flavonoids, Alkaloids, Saponins, Tannins, Terpinoids, Steroids, Phlobataninns, Glycosides.

Fluorescence Quenching Measurement

Fluorescence quenching measurement was done by using the well-known Stern-Volmer equation (Deng and Liu, 2012)

$$\frac{F_0}{F} = 1 + K_{sv}[Q] = 1 + K_q\tau_0[Q] \quad (1)$$

Hence, Eq. (2) was used to get a mean of K_{sv} by linear regression i.e a plot of $\frac{F_0}{F}$ against [Q].

Inhibition Assay for Human salivary α -amylase Activity

The technique developed by modified by Alqahtani *et al.* (2019) was used for the human α -amylase inhibition assay.

Thermodynamics Parameters and Nature of the Binding Forces

K_a was determined using Scatchard analysis from equation (2), (Hu *et al.*, 2004) and their values were obtained from the regression plot of Eq. (2).

$$\log \frac{F_0 - F}{F} = \log K_a + n \log [Q] \quad (2)$$

where K_a is the binding constant and [Q] is the concentration of the quencher (extract)

The dissociation constant (K_d) was determined based on Eq. (3)

$$\Delta F = \frac{F_{max} + [I]}{K_d + [I]} \quad (3)$$

The acting forces between human salivary α -amylase and *Chrysophyllum albidium* extract

$$\ln K_a = \frac{-\Delta H}{RT} + \frac{\Delta S}{R} \quad (4)$$

The values of ΔH and ΔS are obtained from the slope and intercept of the linear plot of $\ln K_a$ versus $1/T$.

The values of free energy change (ΔG) at different temperature were calculated from the following equation:

$$\Delta G = \Delta H - T\Delta S = -RT \ln K_a \quad (5)$$

RESULTS

Phytochemical Screening of Ethanolic Seed Extract of *Chrysophyllum albidium*

The results presented in Table 1 and 2 indicates that the ethanolic seed extract of *Chrysophyllum albidium* contains certain phytochemicals: flavonoids, phenols, alkaloids, tannins, terpenoids, steroids and saponin, present in varying amount.

Determination of α -amylase Inhibitory Property of Ethanolic Seed Extract of *Chrysophyllum albidium*.

The results in Figure 1 shows the ability of the extract to inhibit α -amylase at different concentration when compared with standard inhibitor acarbose.

Fluorescence Emission Spectra

The equilibrium binding study of *Chrysophyllum albidium* extract with HSAmy at different temperature of 15-40 °C, pH 6.8 was explored (Figure 2). The peak of the maximum emission wavelength of HSAmy in the absence of *Chrysophyllum albidium* extract was 345 nm after excitation at 280 nm. The fluorescence spectra shape, peak and intensity were highly repeatable in the solvent used. The fluorescence intensity of HSAmy gradually decreases as the concentration of *Chrysophyllum albidium* extract increases, indicating the binding of *Chrysophyllum albidium* extract to HSAmy. The spectra indicate that the quenching of HSAmy by the extract produces a concentration-dependent decrease in intrinsic tryptophan fluorescence of HSAmy. There was red (bathochromic) shift from 346 nm-357nm in the maximum emission spectra of HSAmy. This result established that there was an interaction between *Chrysophyllum albidium* extract and HSAmy.

Thermodynamics Parameters and Nature of the Binding Forces

According to the binding constants at the six temperatures, the thermodynamic parameters were determined from the Van't Hoff equation (equation 5). From the slope and intercept of the plot, the enthalpy change (ΔH) and entropy change (ΔS) of the reaction are estimated and presented in Table 4.6. Both the positive values of ΔH and ΔS implies that hydrophobic force is the dominant force stabilizing the complex formed. The negative values of ΔG at all temperatures studied implies that the interaction was a spontaneous process.

Table 1: Phytochemical Screening of Ethanolic Seed Extract of *Chrysophyllum albidium*.

Phytochemicals	Qualitative screening
Saponin	+
Phenol	+
Terpenoid	+
Alkaloid	+
Flavonoid	+
Steroids	+
Tannin	+

Key

+ Present

ND Not detected

Table 2: Quantitative phytochemical screening

Steroids	Saponin	Tannin	Terpenoid	Alkaloid	Phenol	Flavonoid
$\mu\text{g/g}$	$\mu\text{g/g}$	$\mu\text{g/g}$	$\mu\text{g/g}$	$\mu\text{g/g}$	$\mu\text{g GAE/g}$	$\mu\text{g (QE)/g}$

0.7642± 0.72

1.93677±0.6 78.0180±1.2 0.0630±0.4 1.83510±1.5 4.7403±0.6 1.5729±0.7
 7 2 6 5 4 5

Results are expressed as Mean ± standard deviation (n=3), values are ($p < 0.05$) significantly different.

Table 3: Thermodynamics and Binding Parameters of *Chrysophyllum albidum* seed extract with HSAmy

Temperature (K)	$K_a \times 10^4$ (L.mol ⁻¹)	$K_d \times 10^{-4}$ (L.mol ⁻¹)	$K_{SV} \times 10^4$ (L.mol ⁻¹)	ΔH (kJmol ⁻¹)	ΔS (Jmol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	ΔG (kJmol ⁻¹)
288	2.67	4.68	1.48			-24.40
293	2.84	4.41	1.53			-24.98
298	3.03	4.33	1.76	21.22	54.32	-25.57
303	3.14	4.06	2.14			-26.08
308	3.31	3.87	2.16			-26.65
313	3.46	3.76	2.30			-27.20

Figure 1: *Chrysophyllum albidum* α -Amylase inhibitory property

Results are expressed as Mean ± standard deviation (n=3). Values are * ($p < 0.05$) significantly different

Figure 2: Fluorescence emission spectra of human salivary α -amylase [0.28 μ M] in 25 mM citrate phosphate buffer at pH 6.8, 25 $^{\circ}$ C.

DISCUSSION

The phytochemical analysis of the ethanolic seed extract of *Chrysophyllum albidium* revealed the presence of several of phytochemicals (Table 1). These bioactive compounds have been widely reported for their pharmacological properties, particularly in antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and enzyme-inhibitory activities (Imaga *et al.*, 2023; Ujam *et al.*, 2024). Flavonoids and phenols, in particular, are known for their strong radical-scavenging capabilities and ability to modulate various biochemical pathways, including carbohydrate metabolism (Rudrapal *et al.*, 2024). Ogunleye *et al.* (2020) and Arueya and Ugwu, (2017) reported that the presence of these phytochemicals suggests a potential therapeutic application of *Chrysophyllum albidium* in regulating digestive enzymes such as HSAmY.

The concentration-dependent inhibitory ability of ethanolic extract of *C. albidium* against HSAmY indicates that higher extract concentrations resulted in greater enzyme inhibition. The inhibition of HSAmY is a crucial therapeutic approach in managing postprandial hyperglycemia, a characteristic feature of diabetes mellitus (Avwioroko *et al.*, 2020). By slowing down starch digestion and reducing glucose release, *C. albidium* extract may contribute to better glycemic control. Omeje *et al.* (2023) also reported the dose dependent inhibitory action of *C. albidium* ethanolic leaves extract against digestive enzymes. The findings suggest that *C. albidium* could be explored as a natural alternative to synthetic HSAmY inhibitors such as acarbose (Channale *et al.*, 2016), which are commonly used in diabetes management but are often associated with gastrointestinal side effects.

Fluorescence spectroscopy remains useful for studying biochemical interactions. Fluorescence is the process of photon emission as a result of the return of an electron in a higher energy orbital back to a lower orbital. Fluorescence measurements among a variety of spectroscopic tools can yield plenty of information of the binding of proteins and/or small molecules to proteins, such as the binding mechanism, type, binding parameters, conformational changes, etc. (Kolawole, 2017). Quenching of the fluorescence indicates reduction of the fluorescence intensity of a given

fluorophore via different molecular interactions including excited-state reactions, molecular rearrangements, energy transfer, ground state complex formation, and collisional quenching (dos Santos Rodrigues *et al.*, 2023). The fluorophores in protein are tryptophan, tyrosine and phenylalanine. However, tryptophan contributes maximally to the fluorescence (Falese *et al.*, 2021). Hence, the quenching potential of *C. albidium* against the intrinsic fluorescence intensity of HSAmy was evaluated. The fluorescence quenching of HSAmy was carried out before and after the addition of a concentration series of *C. albidium* under simulative physiological salivary conditions.

HSAmy has a strong fluorescence emission at 345 nm upon excitation at 280 nm. The addition of *C. albidium*, caused fluorescence quenching of HSAmy fluorescence emission spectra (Figure 2), with a bathochromic shift in the emission wavelength of HSAmy reflecting a binary complex formed between *C. albidium* and HSAmy. Also, the quenching solely depends on the concentration of *C. albidium* extract. Fluorescence quenching is often used to study protein-ligand interactions, and a decrease in fluorescence intensity typically indicates a structural change in the enzyme upon binding to the inhibitor. The quenching effect highlights the ability of the extract's bioactive components to effectively bind to HSAmy, thereby interfering with its activity (Avwioroko *et al.*, 2020).

From the result presented in Table 3, it was observed that the binding constant (K_a) increased with an increase in temperature, which indicated that the binding is an endothermic process (Alsaif *et al.*, 2020) and the capacity of *C. albidium* binding to HSAmy is enhanced with the increasing temperature. The large values of K_a found suggest that the complexation of *C. albidium* with HSAmy is highly favorable (Kolawole *et al.*, 2018). The K_{sv} values (Table 3) indicates that mixed quenching initiates the probable quenching mechanism of *C. albidium* and HSAmy. In addition, upon increasing the temperature of reaction, it was observed that the value of K_{sv} increases. The obtained results suggest that the rise in the temperature of the reaction mixture induced faster diffusion and larger amounts of dynamic quenching.

CONCLUSION

The findings from this study demonstrate that *Chrysophyllum albidium* seed extract exhibits significant human α -amylase inhibitory properties due to its rich phytochemical composition. The extract's ability to interact with the enzyme and alter its structural conformation as confirmed by fluorescence quenching, highlights its potential as a natural α -amylase inhibitor. These results indicate that *Chrysophyllum albidium* could be explored as a functional food ingredient or a natural therapeutic agent for diabetes management by controlling postprandial hyperglycemia.

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